

ANALYSIS OF DATA ON COVID-19 IN ALBANIA FOR THE FIRST QUARTER OF 2020 AND 2021

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Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is a contagious disease caused by a virus, the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The first known case was identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019.^[5] The disease quickly spread worldwide, resulting in the COVID-19 pandemic.

The symptoms of COVID-19 are variable but often include fever,^[6] cough, headache,^[7] fatigue, breathing difficulties, loss of smell, and loss of taste.^{[8][9][10]} Symptoms may begin one to fourteen days after exposure to the virus. At least a third of people who are infected do not develop noticeable symptoms.^[11] Of those who develop symptoms noticeable enough to be classified as patients, most (81%) develop mild to moderate symptoms (up to mild pneumonia), while 14% develop severe symptoms (dyspnea, hypoxia, or more than 50% lung involvement on imaging), and 5% develop critical symptoms (respiratory failure, shock, or multiorgan dysfunction).^[12] Older people are at a higher risk of developing severe symptoms. Some people continue to experience a range of effects (long COVID) for months after recovery, and damage to organs has been observed.^[13] Multi-year studies are underway to further investigate the long-term effects of the disease.^[13]

COVID-19 transmits when people breathe air contaminated by droplets and small airborne particles containing the virus. The risk of breathing these is highest when people are in close proximity, but they can be inhaled over longer distances, particularly indoors. Transmission can also occur if contaminated fluids are splashed or sprayed in the eyes, nose, or mouth, or, more rarely, via contaminated surfaces. People remain contagious for up to 20 days and can spread the virus even if they do not develop symptoms.^{[14][15]}

Testing methods for COVID-19 to detect the virus's nucleic acid include real-time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (rRT-PCR),^{[16][17]} transcription-mediated amplification,^{[16][17][18]} and reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP)^{[16][17]} from a nasopharyngeal swab.^[19]

Several COVID-19 vaccines have been approved and distributed in various countries, which have initiated mass vaccination campaigns. Other preventive measures include physical or social distancing, quarantining, ventilation of indoor spaces, use of face masks or coverings in public, covering coughs and sneezes, hand washing, and keeping unwashed hands away from the face. While work is underway to develop drugs that

inhibit the virus, the primary treatment is symptomatic. Management involves the treatment of symptoms through supportive care, isolation, and experimental measures.

This project consists of analyzing data about the Coronavirus as a global phenomenon. We will develop the analysis based on the databases updated from the beginning of this pandemic until the moment we are here. Indicators presented in the selected database are:

- ❖ The number of confirmed cases of Covid-19
- ❖ Number of deaths
- ❖ Number of recovered.

The analysis that we will present below consists of these points:

1. A general study to see which countries are most affected in relation to the mentioned high indicators (Graphic representation of them in %)
2. A presentation of the total data for Albania. (Their graphic presentation)
3. Comparison of the data of the 1st QUARTER of 2020 with the 1st QUARTER of 2021 for Albania. (Their graphic representation)
4. Comparison of Albania with another country in the region such as Slovenia. (Their graphic presentation)
5. Comparison of Albania with a developed country like Germany to see the reactions to the policies followed. (Their graphic presentation)

COVID-19 is an infectious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The disease has spread globally since 2019, resulting in the 2019-2020 COVID pandemic. The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared the 2019-2020 coronavirus outbreak a pandemic and a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC). Since the beginning of this pandemic, the world has been involved in a situation where all countries are in a state with a high number of affected and high death tolls in reference to the period when it appeared in the world. This is the reason why the curiosity to analyze what happened during this pandemic year is high.

We have chosen to analyze our country as the interest is high to really know, based on the data we have available, what has happened during this period in Albania with Covid-19, in this way we can understand how the country's reaction has been to measures taken.

The database on which we worked and analyzed is that of times.series.19.covid.cvse, which presents the

figures for confirmations, deaths and recoveries for the period January 22, 2020 - March 01, 2022

The packages used during this analysis are:

- dply,
- tidyverse,
- lubricants,
- ggplot2,
- coronavirus,
- totally

Precisely to see these figures and these results, we will look at the graphs below, first referring to all the

countries, in order to clearly distinguish where the highest impact of this pandemic has been.

The number of cases for the whole world continues to increase as well as the number of recoveries despite the fact that the growth may be slower recently. Below we can see concretely that each state has had the highest number of infected, illustrated through a graph which shows the percentage of these states in the total cases.

Confirmations for Top10

From the graph we get a complete picture of the situation of the countries with the highest number of infected and we notice that the United States of America is at the top of the list with about 38.8% of the number of infected compared to the total or 28,663,108 confirmed cases in total .

India ranks second with about 15.1% of the number of infected or 11,112,241 confirmed cases in total.

Meanwhile, below we give a situation of these same states with the excess number of recoveries compared to total recoveries and over the number of deaths compared to total deaths.

Top 10 Recoveries

In terms of the number of recovered among these 10 countries, India holds the first place with approx 34.1% over the total number of recoveries or 10,786,452 total recoveries.

In second place is Brazil with 29.8% of the total number of recoveries or 10,587,001.

Number of deaths Top10

If we look at the ranking according to the number of deaths of the Top10, we see that the United States of America has the highest number with about 34.6% of the total number of deaths or 514,522 in total. In second place is Brazil with about 17.2% of the total number of

deaths or 255,720 in total. The high number of infections in these countries also refers to the high number of population they have compared to other countries. Cases in relation to the population

	Confirmuar	Death	Recovered
USA	8.98%	0.16%	6.21%
India	0.81%	0.01%	0.79%
Brazil	5.25%	0.13%	4.64%

A presentation of the total data for Albania. (Their graphic presentation)

From the graph above, where the situation in Albania is presented for the entire period 2020-2021, referring to all three indicators, we notice that the number of confirmed cases was initially low, it seems that the tests were less based on the lack of conditions and the creation of suitable ground for condition management. With the addition of tests, the number of confirmed cases increases. In total, until 01.03.2021 we have:

- 111,301 confirmed
- 1'897 died,
- 73,610 completed.

The graph shows a high number of recoveries and in relation to confirmed cases, mortality, although presented in the graph with low values, still continues to be high, based on the number of confirmations and the total population.

Comparison of the data of the 1st QUARTER of 2020 with the 1st QUARTER of 2021 for Albania. (Their graphic representation)

Analyzing the figures for Albania based on quarters, it is easier to identify the reaction that our country has had in relation to Covid-19 from the appearance of this pandemic until today. The division consists of the first quarter of 2020 when the quarantine began and the appearance of the first cases in Albania with the first quarter of 2021 where we are still in order to compare the situation then with today.

Quarter 1/2020 - Albania (22.01.2021 - 22.04.2021)

From the graph we made, we noticed that the curves of the three indicators are at very low values and

very close to each other until March 9, 2020, since until those moments there were also the first tracked manifestations of the virus in our country, at least confirmed from the tests done. From the database with the figures presented, Albania up to this date results in 0 confirmed cases, 0 deaths and 0 recoveries. On March 9, the confirmation of the first infected persons begins, whereupon the Health Supervisory Committee gave the alarm and the government quarantined the whole country. At the climax of this quarter, Albania has 638 confirmed cases and 27 deaths, which shows that in a very short time the numbers increased.

Quarter 1 /2021-Albania (29.11.2020-01.03.2021)

In the first quarter of 2021, we notice a graph different from that of the first quarter of 2020. The graphical presentation shows that the curves of the indicators taken in the study are already far from each other, although the trend continues to be upward. With the increase in tests, the number of confirmed cases has also increased, as can be seen from the curve presented in the graph.

It looks like the country is experiencing the second wave of the pandemic. In terms of deaths, the curve is an increasing curve, but not at a very fast rate within the quarter itself, but compared to the first months of 2020, the number of dead has increased significantly.

The total number of deaths at the beginning of the period is 798, while at the end of the period the total number of deaths reaches 1,867, which indicates that for this period we have a total of 1,099 deaths, compared to the first quarter of 2020, which had a number deaths of 123 people, we say that the difference is almost 1000 more deaths.

It is also noted that the curve of the recovered is in a progressive increase. The difference that can be seen between the graphs lies in the fact that the curve of confirmed cases and recoveries in the first quarter of 2020 experience a marked increase, while in the first quarter of 2021 the curves are somewhat more linear in their growth from the beginning of the period to the end

Comparison of Albania with another country in the region such as Slovenia. (Their graphic representation)

Quarter 1 /2020-Slovenia (22.01.2021-22.04.2021)

If we do the same analysis for Slovenia, we notice that the first confirmed case in this country was on 22.01.2020, a few days later than in Albania. From the graph, we understand that even though the beginning of the cases happened a little later, the curve of the infected has a relatively high percentage, which means

that the number of cases has increased at a faster rate compared to our country.

At the end of the quarter, the number of infected people was specifically 1,334 out of 604, which was a difference of 730 in Albania. What we noticed in this chart is the number of recoveries, which is very low compared to the total number of confirmations as well as with the number of recoveries in Albania.

Quarter 1/2021-Slovenia (29.11.2020-01.03.2021)

During the first semester for 2021, we see that the number of confirmed cases increases as well as the number of recoveries, but for both this increase is moderate and both lines run parallel to each other and we see that in the end the number of infections is 190,324

while that of 175,210 recoveries, a significant number of those affected have recovered.

We have an improvement in terms of the number of recovered persons. The number of deaths follows the same line throughout the three semesters where it is clear that it is at low levels with around 3,854 at the end

of the period. This is because at the very beginning of this period, Slovenia declared a state of emergency with the possibility of further strengthening the epidemiological measures.

Comparison of Albania with a developed country like Germany to see the reactions to the policies followed. (Their graphic presentation)

Quarter 1/2021-Germany

Another approach in this analysis is related to the comparison of Albania with a developed country with a high number of population to see how the indicator curve is presented. Germany is one of the most developed countries in the world and in Europe with a number of population relatively high to the approach with this country would make us understand how the policies followed affect these countries. During this period

of the pandemic, Germany has had quite high numbers of affected and deaths. Looking at the graph of the first quarter of 2020 for Germany, we notice that the curves start to increase significantly in March 2020, this is common with Albania and almost throughout the world the emergence of the pandemic occurred in this period. Compared to Albania, the number of confirmed cases starts earlier than March, although not very high values.

In this first quarter, the total number of confirmed cases for Germany is 24,873 and the number of deaths is 94, which shows that the response to the policies followed by Germany has been good, unlike Albania which, although it had a higher number small number of confirmations, deaths are high in the report. The curve of the recovered also appears to be increasing, but with small steps.

Quarter 1/2021-Germany

The graph for this period for Germany shows a linear growth and quite close to each other of the curve of confirmed and recovered. The curves move parallel to each other, so the number of people cured has increased significantly. Germany in the first months of 2021 has a percentage of cured cases of about 92% cured in relation to confirmed ones, while for Albania for the same

period there is a percentage of about 65% cured in relation to confirmed ones with Covid 19. This shows that the management of the situation by Germany is fruitful and if.

As for the number of deaths, the curve is increasing since the second wave has brought high numbers for all European countries

Conclusions for point 5

Looking at the analysis made and based on the general interpretations that can be given to the constructed graphs, we can say that many factors, but mainly medicine and quarantine policies have had a

great impact on the approach to the Covid-19 pandemic. Germany is a very powerful country in terms of development in medicine and we can clearly see from the number of recoveries or deaths in relation to the

confirmed ones, the impact this key sector has had on the numbers. Contrary to the number of confirmed cases, Albania has a low number of recoveries, brought about by several influencing factors, as well as a relatively high number compared to the number of infected in the country.

The presentation of the analysis in the quarters of 2020 and 2021 gives us a clearer picture of the impact of the pandemic on the figures from the beginning of this pandemic and today.

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